

THE CONQUEST OF CENTRAL ASIA BY THE ARABS

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Annotation: *The martial art of the Arab h alifah . In the 7th and 8th centuries, a large united theocratic state of Arab tribes emerged in the Middle East . The Arab tribes have been known to the neighboring peoples since the third millennium BC.*

Key words: *Arab culture has long been of local importance and has not gone beyond the Arabian Peninsula.*

The martial art of the Arab Caliphate. In the VII-VIII centuries, a large united theocratic state of Arab tribes was formed in the Middle East. The Arab tribes have been known to the neighboring peoples since the third millennium BC. The culture of the Arabs had long been of local importance and did not extend beyond the Arabian Peninsula. According to the nature of their occupation, the Arab tribes were divided into three groups: the *Bedouins* (nomadic pastoral tribes), the *fallahs* (settled peasant tribes), and the *semi-fallahs* (semi-nomadic tribes). The Bedouins were engaged in camel-breeding, horse-breeding, and sheep-breeding. Their horsemanship later served as the basis for the formation of Arab cavalry. The Fallachians lived in the oases, engaged in farming, and were a good contingent to fill the ranks of infantry.

The development of trade led to the creation of major centers, such as Mecca and Medina.

The Arabs have long been famous for their fighting. Every adult was an Arab warrior. The sheikhs and saids, famous for their bravery and initiative, had their own small detachments, which later led to the creation of the *caliphate* . Caliph, Islam, which emerged in the seventh century.

A good and basic part of the Arab army was the cavalry, which was light and the Arab state was formed as a result of the unification of the tribes and their occupation of the neighboring territories. In the first half of the seventh century, the Arab caliphate emerged. The Arab armies crushed the Byzantines

and soon conquered Iran, which was weakened in the war with Byzantium. The Arab state became the most powerful state during the reign of the Umayyad dynasty (661–750). By this time the Arabs had overcome the resistance of the Berber tribe, conquered North Africa, and later the Vestigothic kingdom of the Iberian Peninsula, and invaded Gaul, but were crushed by the Franks in a battle near Puate. At the same time, the Arabs successfully waged wars with Byzantium, the Khazars, and the peoples of northwestern India. Throwing the Caspians behind the Caucasus Mountains, they became firmly established in Azerbaijan, Eastern Georgia, and Armenia. Moving east, the Arabs conquered Central Asia-Khorezm and Sogdiana in the middle of the VIII century. (Samarkand) , Tokharistan (the northern territories of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Afghanistan , later called Bactria) , conquered Tashkent , approached the borders of western China, and established themselves in Central Asia. During this period, the Arab Caliphate surpassed the territory of the heyday of the Roman Empire in the breadth of its territory. The capital of the Umayyad caliphate was Damascus. In the occupied territories, the Arabs forcibly converted to Islam.

The fighting order of the Arab army consisted of five parts: the avant-garde, the center - what the Arabs called the "heart", the right and left wings and the rear guard. Both wings were blocked by cavalry. In the Arab army, cavalry usually moved on camels or horses and was several times smaller in number than infantry. High mobility was a hallmark of the Arab armies. Given this quality, the command has made extensive use of the principle of sudden strikes. The battle regimes of the Arabs, scattered along the front and in the depths, provided high tactical maneuverability and the development of the battle from within. In wars, the Arabs made extensive use of ambush, raids, and sudden attacks, often in the morning, which was the strongest period of sleep. In 750, the Abbasid dynasty came to power and ruled until 1258. H The capital of the caliphate was moved to Baghdad . During the Abbasid period, the caliphate reached a high level of development, during which time the structure of the Arab armed forces was completed. Now they have a permanent army. The basis of the standing army was the caliph's personal guard. Each detachment of the Arab Guard was divided into the same heavy cavalry. Heavy cavalymen had long spears, swords, battle axes, battle axes, and defensive weapons. Light cavalry is armed with bullet bows and long, slender darts.

The Arabs had both heavy and y light infantry. Heavy infantry were armed with spears, swords, and shields: they fought in a deepened line. The Arab warriors had swords made of such fine steel that they tore the enemy's horse with a single blow. Infantry archers often moved in a spreading line, with two bows and 30, hardwood, iron-tipped sharpened arrowheads.

The organizational structure of the Arab army was based on the decimal system. The largest army unit was a detachment of 10,000 led by the Emir. This detachment consisted of 10 military units (1000 warriors in each) divided into hundreds and having their own separate commanders. Each hundred is divided into two half-hundred. The smallest division was the decimal.

At the beginning of the ninth century, the Arabs used mobile clinics - *field infirmaries*. The field infirmary had camels, mattresses to carry the wounded and sick; camels, mules, donkeys, tents, medicine, bandages, and medical personnel. They tied the horses before the trip.

The fighting order of the Arabs was divided along the front and in depth. Each of the battle lines was divided into five sherenga and had allegorical (distracting) names: the first battle line ("Dawn of the Dog") consisted of a scattered line of riders; the second ("Day of Aid") and the third ("night of shaking") battle lines, which were the main forces, were lined up in a checkerboard pattern, consisting of cavalry columns or infantry phalanxes; The fourth line of battle was the general reserve, which included selected detachments designed to protect the commander-in-chief. The common reserve is included in the battle in a final, complex situation. Behind the front are the tools needed for supply. Such a fighting order was weak from behind the front and from the wings.

As they approached the enemy, the cavalry in the vanguard of the Arabs began to fight and slowly began to retreat to the side of their main forces. Heavy infantry lined up at this time. The infantry sat on one knee, defending themselves with shields from the enemy's bows and arrows, and thrust their long spears into the ground, leaning their three sides toward the approaching enemy. Behind the heavy infantry, archers stood and fired their bows at the attacking enemy over their heads. Before the battle, the first battle line was introduced and the enemy tried to inflict casualties on its forces by dispersing the battle order. Then the first battle line was supported by the second battle line. The main forces of the Arabs tended to wage defensive warfare and were the basis for the movement of light cavalry and infantry.

In battle, the Arab armies stood out with intensity and determination. They usually tried to cover the wings of the enemy fighting order. When the enemy was exhausted, they launched a general attack, and then continued the pursuit until the enemy was completely crushed. The persecution was carried out by horsemen.

REFERENCE:

1. Sardorbek No'monjon o'g S. et al. YOSHLAR ONGIDA MILLIY G'OYA VA MAFKURA TUSHUNCHALARI SHAKLLANTIRISH //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 11-15.
2. PERSON, FORMATION OF A. HIGH SPIRITUAL. "FarDU. Faculty of Military Education student."
3. Otakoziyevna G. F. et al. THE IMPORTANT ROLE OF EDUCATION IN EDUCATION OF YOUTH //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 1. – C. 381-383.
4. Sh, Tilavoldiev. "General Didactic Principles of Pedagogical Technologies." Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices 6 (2022): 94-97.
5. Khasanov, N., Yusufjonov, K., Yusupov, A., & Topivoldiyev, J. (2022). PATRIOTISM IS THE HIGHEST VIRTUE AND DIGNITY. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 1(4), 4-7.
6. Khasanov, N., Yusufjonov, K., Yusupov, A., & Topivoldiyev, J. (2022). PATRIOTISM IS A GREAT VALUE. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 2(5), 12-15.
7. Khasanov, N., Yusufjonov, K., Yusupov, A., & Topivoldiyev, J. (2022). EDUCATING THE YOUNG GENERATION IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM. FACTORS. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 2(5), 8-11.
8. Khasanov, N., Yusufjonov, K., Yusupov, A., & Topivoldiyev, J. (2022). THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE FAMILY IN EDUCATING THE YOUNG GENERATION IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 2(5), 1-4.
9. Khasanov, N., Yusufjonov, K., Yusupov, A., & Topivoldiyev, J. (2022). THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF YOUTH IN THE CREATION OF THE ENLIGHTENED SOCIETY" NEW UZBEKISTAN". INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 2(5), 5-7.
10. Khasanov, N., Yusufjonov, K., Yusupov, A., & Topivoldiyev, J. (2022). THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS AND LAWS OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL CULTURE OF MILITARY EDUCATION. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 1(4), 1-3.
11. Khasanov, N., Yusufjonov, K., Yusupov, A., & Topivoldiyev, J. (2022). SPITAMEN'S HORSE CATCHED THE RIVER AND CAUSED ONE OF THE ISLANDS BETWEEN THE RIVER. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 1(4), 8-10.
12. Nurmukhammad, K., Kuyoshbek, Y., Arabboy, Y., & Jasurbek, T. (2022, May). PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY AND ITS SCIENTIFIC AND

THEORETICAL BASIS AND RULES. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 1-6).

13. Nurmukhammad, K., Arabboy, Y., Kuyoshbek, Y., & Jasurbek, T. (2022). THE STRUGGLE AND DEFENSE OF SULTAN JALALIDDIN MANGUBERDI AGAINST MONGOLIA. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 2(17), 1-3.

14. Tojimatovich A. A., Saydaliyevich U. S. Formation Of Science as A Value and Classification of Values //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2021. – T. 3. – C. 172-178.

15. Tojimatovich, Akbarov Anvar, and Ubaydullayev Saidakbar Saydaliyevich. "Formation Of Science as A Value and Classification of Values." Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies 3 (2021): 172-178.

16. Tojimatovich, A. A., & Saydaliyevich, U. S. (2021). Formation Of Science as A Value and Classification of Values. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 3, 172-178.